

Motion planning for long reach manipulation in aerial robotic systems with two arms

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Abstract—In this paper an aerial robotic system with two arms for long reach manipulation (ARS-LRM) while flying is presented. The system consists of a multirotor with a long bar extension that incorporates a lightweight dual arm in the tip. This configuration allows aerial manipulation tasks increasing considerably the safety distance between rotors and manipulated objects. The objective of this work is the development of planning strategies to move the ARS-LRM system for both navigation and manipulation tasks. With this purpose, a simulation environment to evaluate the algorithms under consideration is required. Consequently, the ARS-LRM dynamics has been properly modeled with specific methodologies for multi-body systems. Then, a distributed control scheme that makes use of nonlinear control strategies based on model inversion has been derived to complete the testbed. The motion planning problem is addressed considering jointly the aerial platform and the dual arm in order to achieve wider and safer operating conditions. The operation of the planner is given by an RRT*-based algorithm that optimizes energy and time performance in cluttered environments for both navigation and manipulation tasks. This motion planning strategy has been tested in a realistic industrial scenario given by a riveting task. The satisfactory results of the simulations are presented as a first validation of the proposed approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the numerous applications in which unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) can be used, aerial manipulation is arousing much interest. Potential applications in this field include instrument deployment, maintenance operation and contact inspection in industrial sites in which the access is very dangerous or costly. The motivation is to decrease risks and operational costs in these scenarios with the support of aerial manipulation systems. Small size rotorcraft can indeed access to hard-to-reach places more easily than human operators, avoiding unnecessary risks for industrial workers and allowing inspection and maintenance operations without shut-downs of the facilities (the mandatory safety policy in case of human operation) and the use of scaffolding, cranes and other means.

These new promising applications of aerial robotic systems for manipulation tasks bring also new challenges that are still unresolved. On the one hand, it is necessary to develop new manipulation tools such as adapted arms or grippers that can be seamlessly integrated into the airframe to provide

manipulation capabilities to UAVs. The existing algorithms for operating independently the UAV and the manipulators should be extended for achieving autonomous operation of the integrated system. In this respect, one of the most challenging issues is the development of new methods that consider both the UAV and the manipulator when planning the motion of the complete system. When moving between different locations inside a dense industrial installation, this planning will be essential for the generation of accurate movements close to obstacles. In addition, it will also enable rapid, agile manoeuvres (e.g., using the arm to let the aerial manipulator turn quickly) aiming to approach to the goal location avoiding waste of battery.

Many research works about aerial manipulation have been recently published. [1] presents the design of several lightweight, low-complexity grippers that allow quadrotors to grasp and perch on branches or beams and pick up and transport payloads. In a very different system scale, [2] proposes a system for aerial manipulation, composed of a helicopter and an industrial manipulator. The usage of an industrial manipulator is motivated by practical applications which were identified in different cooperation projects with the industry.

However, among the different contributions focused on aerial manipulation very few of them consider configurations with more than one arm. In [3] a human-size and lightweight dual arm manipulator is integrated in a multirotor platform and tested in outdoor flights. On the other hand, [4] proposes a dual arm aerial manipulator to turn a valve that requires a tightly integrated control scheme between aircraft and both manipulators. The arm-aircraft system for valve turning is validated through flight tests. Concerning theoretical contributions, [5] introduces a generic planar aerial manipulator with any number of arms attached at the center of mass of a UAV. The authors prove that this kind of systems are differentially flat regardless the number of joints of each arm and their kinematic and dynamic parameters. This theory is validated by simulating object grasping and transportation tasks.

On the other hand, although a large amount of works have been focused on the development of control techniques for the system integrating the aerial vehicle and the manipulator devices, not many of them deal with the associated motion planning problem. Furthermore, the existing contributions like [6] usually assume a strong simplification by addressing the planning problem in a decoupled way, i.e. adopting independent planners for the UAV and the manipulators that

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switch their operation according to the mission phase. This means that during the navigation phase, the arm configuration is assumed to be fixed and hence the UAV planner is in charge of planning the motion. In contrast, the manipulation phase is resolved by using the manipulators planners and assuming that the aerial platform is not moving.

This work explores dual arm configurations that guarantee long reach manipulation in those scenarios where the target is far from the operation area of the UAV. In order to meet these requirements a new aerial robotic system with two arms for long reach manipulation (ARS-LRM) is proposed. More precisely, the system consists of a multirotor with a long bar extension that incorporates a lightweight dual arm in the tip (see Fig. 1). Thus, the long bar extension increases considerably the safety distance between rotors and manipulated objects while the dual arm offers extended manipulation capabilities with respect to the single arm configurations existing in the literature.

Figure 1: Aerial robotic system with two arms for long reach manipulation (ARS-LRM).

Concerning the motion planning problem, this paper investigates strategies for the ARS-LRM in cluttered environments in both navigation and manipulation tasks. For this purpose, the aerial platform and the dual arm device are considered jointly within the planner operation, which constitutes a remarkable difference to previous contributions where the planning problem was addressed in a decoupled way. This integrated strategy allows the consideration of a more complete set of system states that in turn will make it possible to achieve wider and safer operating conditions. Regarding the operation basis of the planner, an RRT*-based algorithm that optimizes energy and time performance has been developed.

This paper presents a first proof of concept of the ARS-LRM system described in previous paragraphs. The work begins with Section II presenting the structure of the integrated platform, the corresponding multi-body dynamical model and finally the distributed control approach derived for the system. Then, in Section III the proposed planning algorithm is explained in detail. In order to better illustrate its benefits, Section IV defines a realistic industrial scenario given by a riveting task. After presenting the complete system as well as the motivating scenario, Section V includes several simulations of the planning capabilities of the ARS-LRM system to endorse the validity of the proposed algorithm. Finally, Section VI is devoted to conclusions and future work.

II. MODELING AND CONTROL

A. System Description

As can be seen in Fig. 2, the proposed aerial robotic system for long reach manipulation (ARS-LRM) consists of a multirotor with a long bar extension that incorporates a lightweight dual arm in the tip. This configuration allows aerial manipulation tasks increasing considerably the safety distance between rotors and manipulated objects. Furthermore, the dual arm offers extended manipulation capabilities with respect to the single arm configurations existing in the literature. In this first prototype of the system each separate arm is composed of two links, corresponding the lower one to the end effector, but further extensions of the manipulation chain are considered in future work.

Figure 2: Geometry and mass distribution of the ARS-LRM system.

A planar characterization of the system will serve for establishing a first proof of concept for the ARS-LRM setup. This simplified approach eases the modeling and control developments while maintaining the operation basis of the system. Following this assumption, the multirotor is characterized by a mass m_M , a principal moment of inertia I_{22}^M and dimensions $2d \times w$. Regarding the long bar, its longitude is given by l_P and it is assumed to be aligned with the UAV center of mass M^O at a distance d . The cross-piece in the tip is defined by a length of $2l_C$. The total mass of the long bar and the cross-piece is m_P and will be treated as a punctual mass located where the long bar and the cross-piece intersects for simplicity purposes. Finally, the 2 arms are characterized respectively by the lengths of their links $-l_1$ for upper links and l_2 for lower links- and their masses $-m_1$ and m_2 -, where again the masses will be treated as punctual masses located at the distal end of each link in order to derive more manageable expressions. The values of the aforementioned parameters are shown in Table I.

Table I: ARS-LRM Parameters

	Parameter	Value	Units
Mass and Inertia	m_M	6.5	kg
-	I_{22}^M	0.0933	kg·m ²
-	m_P	0.15	kg
-	m_1	0.06	kg
-	m_2	0.03	kg
Geometry	d	0.1	m
-	w	0.9	m
-	l_P	0.2	m
-	l_C	0.1	m
-	l_1	0.15	m
-	l_2	0.05	m

B. Modeling

According to [7], the dynamics of a multirotor under 20kg is mostly determined by its mechanical model. This paper embraces the same assumption and consequently the behaviour of the ARS-LRM platform will be described by means of the mechanical model of the complete system. To this end, specific methodologies for multi-body systems will be applied below.

Several approaches can be found in the literature to derive equations of motion for mechanical systems. However, Kane's method [8] has proved in [9] to hold some unique advantages over other traditional approaches when addressing multi-body robotic systems like the ARS-LRM under study in this paper.

Figure 3: ARS-LRM model. Configuration variables. In green, the variables selected later for the planning space.

The configuration variables selected as system generalized coordinates are the longitudinal q_1 and vertical q_3 positions of the UAV center of mass M^O in the inertial reference frame N , the multirotor pitch angle q_5 and the joint angles both for left L and right R arms q_7^L , q_7^R and q_8^L , q_8^R (see Fig. 3). Generalized speeds u_i are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} N_{\mathbf{v}}^{M^O} &= u_1 \mathbf{n}_1 + u_3 \mathbf{n}_3 \\ N_{\boldsymbol{\omega}}^M &= u_5 \mathbf{n}_2 \end{aligned} \quad \begin{aligned} M_{\boldsymbol{\omega}}^{R-U} &= u_7^R \mathbf{n}_2 \\ R-U_{\boldsymbol{\omega}}^{R-D} &= u_8^R \mathbf{n}_2 \\ M_{\boldsymbol{\omega}}^{L-U} &= -u_7^L \mathbf{n}_2 \\ L-U_{\boldsymbol{\omega}}^{L-D} &= -u_8^L \mathbf{n}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

which leads to the following kinematic differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{q}_i &= u_i \quad (i = 1, 3, 5) \\ \dot{q}_j^k &= u_j^k \quad (j = 7, 8; k = R, L) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Figure 4: ARS-LRM model. Forces and torques applied to the system.

Regarding forces and torques exerted on the ARS-LRM system (see Fig. 4), the rotors generate a resultant lifting force $F_3 \mathbf{a}_3$ applied at the multirotor center of mass M^O as well as a torque $T_2 \mathbf{a}_2$ applied to rigid body M . On the other hand, control actions governing the manipulator are given by the torques applied to the arm joints $T_7^R \mathbf{a}_2$, $T_8^R \mathbf{a}_2$, $-T_7^L \mathbf{a}_2$ and $-T_8^L \mathbf{a}_2$.

Application of Kane's method through MotionGenesis software [10] leads to the following dynamic differential equations for translation and rotation, where \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{D} are dense matrices depending on the configuration variables q_5 , q_7^R , q_8^R , q_7^L , q_8^L and the system parameters defined in Table I and g is the gravity acceleration.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_1 \\ \dot{u}_3 \\ \dot{u}_5 \\ \dot{u}_7^R \\ \dot{u}_8^R \\ \dot{u}_7^L \\ \dot{u}_8^L \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A} \begin{bmatrix} F_3 \\ T_2 \\ T_7^R \\ T_8^R \\ T_7^L \\ T_8^L \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{B} \begin{bmatrix} (u_5)^2 \\ (u_7^R)^2 \\ (u_8^R)^2 \\ (u_7^L)^2 \\ (u_8^L)^2 \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{C} \begin{bmatrix} u_5 u_7^R \\ u_5 u_8^R \\ u_5 u_7^L \\ u_5 u_8^L \\ u_7^R u_8^R \\ u_7^L u_8^L \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{D} g \quad (3)$$

C. Control

After modeling the ARS-LRM system, a distributed control scheme has been derived to provide the system with the capacity of executing navigation and manipulation manoeuvres. The objective is the completion of the simulation environment that will allow the investigation of new planning strategies to properly command the ARS-LRM platform. With this purpose, a basic control structure that makes use of nonlinear control strategies based on model inversion shall suffice to complete the testbed.

Regarding the multirotor, the control scheme is inspired by [7] and consists in linearizing the system through model inversion and applying PID control laws to the resultant dynamics. The underlying principle of control will be the adjustment of the multirotor lifting force vector, in order to generate the translational accelerations required to reduce position error. A general overview of the control scheme is shown in Fig. 5, where D_{13}^{-1} , K_5^{-1} and D_5^{-1} blocks represent, respectively, the inversions of the translational dynamics, rotational kinematics and rotational dynamics.

Figure 5: Scheme of the UAV controller.

The control strategy selected for each arm is again based on linearization through model inversion and PD control, which yields a nonlinear control law capable of commanding the link positions of both arms. The schematic representation of this approach is shown in Fig. 6 where D_{78}^{-1} represents the block in charge of inverting arm dynamics and torques T_7^R , T_8^R , T_7^L and T_8^L correspond to the output signals of the controller.

Figure 6: Scheme of each arm controller.

The parameters of the controller have been tuned by means of the classic pole assignment method. The selected values constitute a trade-off that guarantees a proper dynamics range while the common mechanical limitations of this kind of systems are not overreached.

III. MOTION PLANNER

Sampling based planners like the family of RRT algorithms [11] have demonstrated high potential in finding fast solutions for high-dimensional robots [12]. Furthermore, some of these methods bring the possibility of generating motion plans that optimize certain cost functions, as for the case of RRT* variations [13]. This makes it possible to find an optimal solution in terms of a specific metric. Taking all these considerations into account, an RRT*-based algorithm that optimizes energy and time performance has been selected for the ARS-LRM system.

Another determining factor for planner performance is the planning space considered when exploring the different possibilities of motion. In this work the planner explores jointly the configuration variables of the aerial platform (with the exception of pitch angle q_5) and the dual arm (variables in green color in Fig. 3). This integrated strategy allows the consideration of a more complete set of system states. In this way, it is possible to achieve wider and safer operating conditions since equivalent configurations in terms of final effector positions can be differentiated according to the positions of both the multirotor and the intermediate links.

The pseudocode of the common structure of an RRT* algorithm is shown in the code fragment 1. In order to apply this general structure to the ARS-LRM system, some of the intermediate functionalities have been customized for the problem under study. These particular developments will be dealt with in detail hereafter.

Algorithm 1 RRT* algorithm

Input: $map, param$

Output: $trajectory$

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1:  $Tree \leftarrow INITIALIZATION(map, param)$ 
2: for  $i = 1$  to  $iter_{max}$  do
3:    $x_{rand} \leftarrow SAMPLE()$ 
4:    $x_{nearest} \leftarrow NEAREST(Tree, x_{rand})$ 
5:    $x_{new} \leftarrow STEER(x_{nearest}, x_{rand})$ 
6:   if  $\sim COLLISION(x_{nearest}, x_{new}, map)$  then
7:      $x_{near} \leftarrow NEAR(Tree, x_{new})$ 
8:      $Tree \leftarrow ADD(x_{nearest}, x_{near}, x_{new})$ 
9:      $Tree \leftarrow REWIRE(x_{near}, x_{new})$ 
10:  end if
11: end for
12:  $trajectory \leftarrow TRAJECTORY(Tree)$ 

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A. Computation of the Nearest Node

The $NEAREST(Tree, x_{rand})$ function finds the nearest node $x_{nearest}$ to the random state x_{rand} generated in the sampling-based exploration of the planning space. Since nodes include state information both for multirotor and dual arm accordingly with the integrated operation basis of the planner, there will be two different measurements for calculating the nearest node: the difference in position for the multirotor and the difference in angle for the arm joints. Thus, there appears the need of defining a homogenizing metric. The reference velocities u_{ref} (for the UAV) and w_{ref} (for the joints) have been defined with this purpose of transforming the heterogeneous measurements into a common metric given by the time magnitude required for each system component to move between the configurations associated with the nodes under analysis. The equations corresponding to this normalization approach are presented below:

$$t_{UAV} = \frac{\sqrt{(\Delta q_1)^2 + (\Delta q_3)^2}}{u_{ref}}$$

$$t_{ARMS} = \frac{\max(|\Delta q_7^R|, |\Delta q_8^R|, |\Delta q_7^L|, |\Delta q_8^L|)}{w_{ref}}$$

$$x_{nearest} = \min_{x \in Tree} (\max(t_{UAV}|_x, t_{ARMS}|_x)) \quad (4)$$

where Δq_i denotes the increment in variable q_i when going from the tree node x to the sampled node x_{rand} , that is, $\Delta q_i = q_i^{rand} - q_i^x$.

B. Collision Checking

The $COLLISION(x_{nearest}, x_{new}, map)$ function checks if the branch that would link two nodes produces some collision with the obstacles included in the map. To this end, a representative set of intermediate configurations between the nodes is generated using interpolation. Then, each intermediate configuration is investigated to see if any part of the system collides with the obstacles defined in the scenario.

This operation deserves special attention since it plays an important role in the advanced functionality of the ARS-LRM planner that allows differentiating equivalent configurations in terms of final effector positions according to the positions of both the multirotor and the intermediate links. The consideration of the different geometries of the system components, together with joint exploration of the planning space for both system components, are crucial features in this respect. Concerning the former, simplified models that alleviate the computational burden of collision checking but maintaining at the same time their capability to express the heterogeneity existing in the geometry of the different parts, are the desirable option. To this end, the multirotor has been considered rectangularly shaped while the dual arm and the long bar extension are modeled by rectilinear bars with negligible section. Regarding the obstacles, all of them have been considered round.

Another aspect that requires further consideration is the algorithm selected for detecting the collisions. In the case of

the multirotor, the approach is straightforward since it only requires checking whether the position of the center of mass is within the limits of the rectangular region that produces collisions with the obstacle (see Fig. 7).

Figure 7: Scheme of the collision checking for the multirotor.

In contrast, the collision management for the extension bar and the dual arm consists of translating the collision condition to the angular space as shown in Fig. 8. In this way, the obstacle is characterized in terms of the minimum and maximum link angle that may produce a collision. Then, taking into account also the distance to the obstacle, it is possible to check the collision with a considerably reduction in the computational load with respect to standard procedures.

Figure 8: Scheme of the collision checking for the right upper link.

C. Computation of the Set of Near Nodes

The $NEAR(Tree, x_{new})$ function finds the set of tree nodes x_{near} that satisfy simultaneously the following conditions with respect to their distances to the new candidate node x_{new} : the difference in multirotor position is less than threshold γ_{UAV} and the differences in link orientations are all less than threshold γ_{ARMS} . This definition can be expressed mathematically as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{UAV} &= \sqrt{(\Delta q_1)^2 + (\Delta q_3)^2} \\ \rho_{ARMS} &= \max(|\Delta q_7^R|, |\Delta q_8^R|, |\Delta q_7^L|, |\Delta q_8^L|) \end{aligned}$$

$$x_{near} = x \in Tree / \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \rho_{UAV}|_x \leq \gamma_{UAV} \\ \rho_{ARMS}|_x \leq \gamma_{ARMS} \end{array} \right. \quad (5)$$

where Δq_i denotes the increment in variable q_i when going from the tree node x to the new candidate node x_{new} , that is, $\Delta q_i = q_i^{new} - q_i^x$.

D. Cost Functions

In order to apply the RRT* optimization sequence within the $ADD(x_{nearest}, x_{near}, x_{new})$ and $REWIRE(x_{near}, x_{new})$ functions, two different cost indices have been defined: the operation time of the complete system (CF_T), and the linear and angular displacements produced in the multirotor and the arm joints respectively (CF_E). These cost indices can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} CF_T &= \max(t_{UAV}, t_{ARMS}) \\ CF_E &= p_1 \cdot \rho_{UAV} + p_2 \cdot \sigma_{ARMS} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where t_{UAV} and t_{ARMS} were defined in equations (4); ρ_{UAV} was defined in equations (5); $\sigma_{ARMS} = |\Delta q_7^R| + |\Delta q_8^R| + |\Delta q_7^L| + |\Delta q_8^L|$ with Δq_i denoting the increment in variable q_i between the nodes in which the cost function is being evaluated ($\Delta q_i = q_i^{to} - q_i^{from}$); and $p_{1,2}$ are two weighting parameters that allow the prioritization of movements with minimum displacements in the multirotor or the dual arm.

IV. APPLICATION SCENARIO: RIVETING TASK

In order to demonstrate the validity of the motion planning strategy presented in previous section, the algorithm will be tested in a realistic industrial scenario given by a riveting task. The schematic description of the scenario is shown in Fig. 9, where coloured circles correspond to pipes existing in the industrial facility and surrounding circumferences denote the safety regions whose violation would be treated as a collision. As can be seen, the ARS-LRM system will be commanded to place two rivets with its right arm (target points marked in red) while the left arm provides visual feedback by pointing a visual camera integrated as end effector (see Fig. 1). In this first proof of concept, the riveting operations will assume ideal conditions, i.e. absence of interaction forces, since force control has not been implemented yet in the ARS-LRM system to facilitate the analysis of the planner results.

Figure 9: Application scenario given by a riveting task.

The achievement of the riveting objectives defined previously requires the execution of certain intermediate operations that include both navigation and manipulation manoeuvres:

- 1) **Navigation phase:** this phase corresponds to the system displacement required to reach an observation position over the riveting area. After this, a short transition phase not requiring planner execution will enforce a ready-to-go configuration for the first riveting manoeuvre that will be accomplished during the manipulation phase.
- 2) **Manipulation phase:** this phase covers the different manoeuvres involved in the manipulation task under consideration, the riveting operation.
 - a) **Rivet placement:** approaching to the target point in the perpendicular direction to the target point plane by the riveting effector integrated in the right arm.

- b) **Release:** opposite manoeuvre to the rivet placement in which the riveting effector leaves the target point, again following the perpendicular direction to the target point plane.
- c) **Switching:** manoeuvre of the complete ARS-LRM system to switch between the ready-to-go configurations for riveting points 1 and 2.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section the RRT*-based algorithm derived for the ARS-LRM system has been used to calculate a motion plan that commands the riveting task presented in the previous section. The index selected for optimization has been the cost function CF_E defined in Section III-D. Furthermore, not only the planned trajectory will be a matter of study but also the trajectory executed by the controlled ARS-LRM model when receiving the former as control reference.

Due to the high dimension of the planning space considered by the ARS-LRM planner (see Fig. 3), a continuous treatment of the variable ranges considered in the sampling operation would lead to significantly elevated values of the execution times required for achieving convergent solutions. The former suggests the adoption of discretization patterns that guarantee bounded execution times for the planner. Table II shows the discretization patterns adopted for the navigation and manipulation phases in the riveting scenario.

Table II: Discretization of the planning-space

Phase	Navigation	Manipulation
Variable	Discretization Pattern	
q_1	$[45, 50, \dots, 275] \text{ cm}$	$[225, 230, \dots, 255] \text{ cm}$
q_3	$[30, 35, \dots, 170] \text{ cm}$	$[80, 85, \dots, 120] \text{ cm}$
q_7^R	$[0, 45, 90]^\circ$	$[30, 40, \dots, 140, 150]^\circ$
q_8^R	Fixed value of 170°	$[-45, 0, 45]^\circ$
q_7^L	$[0, 45, 90]^\circ$	Fixed value of 60°
q_8^L	Fixed value of 170°	Fixed value of 110°

Considering all the above information, the motion planner of the ARS-LRM system has been executed for the riveting scenario. As advanced before, the resultant plan (represented with green lines in the figures) has been also provided to the controlled ARS-LRM system in order to analyze the close-loop behavior of the system (represented with blue lines in the figures) when following the planned trajectory. This simulation work has been carried out in a Matlab-Simulink framework that represents the graphical evolution of the system variables and the corresponding virtual reality animation [14].

The results corresponding to the navigation phase are presented in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. In Fig. 10 the trajectory followed by the ARS-LRM system is illustrated by the dotted line representing the movement of the UAV center of mass M^O . In Fig. 11 the evolution of the planning-space variables, both for the planned trajectory (green line) and the close-loop executed trajectory (blue line), has been shown. As can be observed, the planned trajectory succeeded in commanding efficiently the controlled ARS-LRM system

through the navigation phase without producing collisions with the obstacles existing in the scenario.

Regarding the manipulation phase, Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 illustrate the achieved results. As in the navigation phase, Fig. 12 shows a schematic representation of the manoeuvres associated with the manipulation phase. Similarly, in Fig. 13 the evolution of the planning-space variables, both for the planned trajectory (green line) and the close-loop executed trajectory (blue line), has been represented for this phase. Once again the planned trajectory succeeded in commanding efficiently the controlled ARS-LRM system through the different manipulation manoeuvres involved in the riveting task. It is worth highlighting that Fig. 12 (switching) illustrates how the jointly consideration of the planning space for the multirotor and the dual arm allows the optimization of the switching manoeuvre between the riveting points. More precisely, the motion planner takes advantage of the multirotor vertical displacement to carry out the switching manoeuvre of the riveting effector in a more efficient way.

Figure 10: Navigation phase. The ARS-LRM system navigates through the obstacles. The dotted line represents the simulated center of mass position of the multirotor M^O .

Figure 11: Navigation phase. Representation of the planning-space variables: planned trajectory (green) and executed trajectory (blue).

Figure 12: Manipulation phase. The ARS-LRM system places the first rivet and then switches between the ready-to-go configurations.

Figure 13: Manipulation phase. Representation of the planning-space variables: planned trajectory (green) and executed trajectory (blue).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented motion planning strategies for an aerial robotic system with two arms for long reach manipulation (ARS-LRM). In order to evaluate the algorithms under consideration, a simulation environment that characterizes the system behaviours that are relevant for planner operation was required. Consistently with this requirement, the ARS-LRM platform has been described in detail together with its potential benefits: a considerable increment in the safety distance between rotors and manipulated objects, and the extended manipulation capabilities offered by the dual arm. Taking this description as reference, the dynamics of the system has been modeled with specific methodologies for multi-body systems. Furthermore, a distributed control scheme that makes use of nonlinear control strategies based on model inversion has been derived to complete the testbed.

With respect to the planning approach, several features justify the relevance of this contribution. The aerial platform and the dual arm device have been considered jointly within the planner operation. In this way, it is possible to achieve wider and safer operating conditions since equivalent configurations in terms of final effector positions can be differentiated

according to the positions of both the multirotor and the intermediate links. On the other hand, the planner operation is driven by an RRT*-based algorithm that optimizes energy and time performance in cluttered environments for both navigation and manipulation tasks.

In order to demonstrate the validity of the motion planning strategy presented, the algorithm has been tested in a realistic industrial scenario given by a riveting task. As was discussed in the simulation section, the planned trajectory succeeded in commanding efficiently the controlled ARS-LRM system through navigation and manipulation phases without producing collisions with the obstacles existing in the scenario. These satisfactory results are presented as a first validation of the proposed approach.

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